

Evaluation of the Performance Characteristics of CGLSS II and U.S. NLDN Using Ground-Truth Data From Launch Complex 39B, Kennedy Space Center, Florida

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Abstract— A new comprehensive lightning instrumentation system has been designed for Launch Complex 39B (LC39B) at the Kennedy Space Center (KSC), Florida. This new instrumentation system includes seven synchronized high-speed video cameras, current sensors installed on the nine downconductors of the new LC39B lightning protection system (LPS); four dH/dt, 3-axis measurement stations; and five dE/dt stations composed of two sensors each. The LPS received 8 direct lightning strikes (a total of 19 strokes) from March 31 through December 31 2011. The measured peak currents and locations are compared to those reported by the Cloud-to-Ground Lightning Surveillance System (CGLSS II) and the National Lightning Detection Network (NLDN). Results of comparison are presented and analyzed in this paper.

Keywords—Lightning protection, lightning instrumentation, KSC, NASA, CGLSS, NLDN, ICLRT.

I. INTRODUCTION

After over 40 years of deploying and using Lightning Instrumentation (Lightning Detection and Location Systems) at or around the vicinities of the Kennedy Space Center (KSC) and Cape Canaveral Air Force Station (CCAFS) much has been improved and gained; from monitoring the electric field during the Apollo days (mid-late 1960's) [1] to the precise location of a lightning strike at LC39B (Fig. 1) with the deployment of the LC39B lightning instrumentation system (LIS) in 2011.

Both, the Cloud-to-Ground Lightning Surveillance System (CGLSS II) and the National Lightning Detection Network (NLDN), have been providing lightning detection and location data for KSC and CCAFS with some expected margin of error (both detection and location) since these systems monitor big areas. Even though over the years the location error has

decreased and the detection efficiency has improved, these systems cannot provide accurate lightning location with 100% detection efficiency, which is required when protecting expensive and delicate flight hardware.

The most recent NLDN performance characteristics was evaluated using rocket triggered lightning data from 2004 to 2009 at the International Center for Lightning Research and Testing (ICLRT), Camp Blanding, Florida [2] with the resulting flash and stroke detection efficiencies being 92% and 76%, respectively; the median absolute location error was 308 meters, and the largest error was 4.2 kilometers.

The most recent comparison between CGLSS II and NLDN was performed using historical data from 2005 and 2006 [3] where it was found that the CGLSS II fails to report about 28% of high-current strokes reported by the NLDN and the NLDN fails to report about 17.5% of the low current strokes reported by CGLSS II and their calculated median position difference is 656 meters (for data analyzed over four days).

The LC39B LIS provides precise location and total detection for only a relatively small area at KSC (LC39B and its vicinity) but there is a possibility of implementing this system at multiple launch pads (like LC39A and CCAFS), which could all be interconnected, providing 100% detection efficiency for all the launch pads within KSC and CCAFS.

II. KSC LIGHTNING LOCATION SYSTEMS DESCRIPTION

A. LC39B LPS, KSC

The LC39B lightning protection system (LPS) and its lightning instrumentation are described in detail in [4] and [5], respectively. The LIS is a 100 megasamples per second event-driven data acquisition (DAQ) system running 24/7 with sub-

microsecond timing accuracy, whose trigger signal can be generated from any of the thirty one (31) ground level sensors (9 downconductor currents, 12 dH/dt, and 10 dE/dt). Additionally a TTL signal from the LC39A LIS has been provided, because the LC39B lightning instrumentation was used to monitor the last two Space Shuttle launches from LC39A. After a qualified trigger is received, the signals of all the ground level sensors are recorded in a 30-millisecond time window with 50% pre-trigger. Additionally, seven¹ high speed video cameras record up to 455 frames at 3,200 frames per second with 50% pre-trigger and a resolution of 1280x800.

Figure 1. Lightning protection system of LC39B, Kennedy Space Center, Florida. Seen at the launch pad is the standby rescue Shuttle during the Hubble repair mission in 2009.

The LC39B LIS data provide the capability of locating lightning strikes by means of:

- Time of Arrival (using dE/dt waveforms)
- Magnetic Direction Finding (using dH/dt waveforms)
- High speed video frames
- Downconductor currents

B. CGLSS II, CCAFS

The first Cloud-to-Ground Lightning Surveillance System (CGLSS) was installed at the KSC-Eastern Range (ER) during the summer of 1979 (before the first shuttle launch, 1981) as a prototype system consisting of three magnetic direction finders. During 1995-1998, the system was converted to a 6-station (see Fig. 2 for sensors location), short-baseline network of medium-gain IMPACT (IMproved Accuracy from Combined Technology) sensors and it currently has an effective range of about 100 kilometers, covering the KSC-ER launch and operation areas, operating 24 hours a day, 7 days a week [1]. Its daily lightning reporting has also seen improvements in recent years [6] and it mainly includes the following parameters:

¹ Originally the system was designed with 6 video cameras and one additional high-speed video camera was temporarily installed (June 2011) about five kilometers southwest of LC39B. This camera was installed atop the Vehicle Assembly Building (VAB) in March 2012.

latitude, longitude, microsecond time, number of sensors used, peak current, and polarity of lightning strike.

Figure 2. Map showing the location of 6 CGLSS II sensors.

The CGLSS II has been working with a reduced network (5 out of 6 sensors) since August of 2009.

C. U.S. NLDN

The U.S. National Lightning Detection Network (NLDN) has been providing real-time, continental-scale lightning information since 1989 and it has undergone several improvements and updates [7]. Fig. 3 shows the sensors located in and around Florida.

Figure 3. Map showing the locations of 15 U.S. National Lightning Detection Network (NLDN) sensors in and around the Florida region as of late 2003. The approximate locations of Camp Blanding (ICLRT) and the Kennedy Space Center (KSC) are also shown. The current network configuration is essentially the same as shown here, except for the additional sensor in the Bahamas installed in mid - 2006 [2].

The NLDN currently consists of a nationwide network of 114 Vaisala Thunderstorm CG Enhanced Lightning Sensors LS7001 [8], specifying a median location accuracy of 250-500 meters, which basically use a low frequency combined

Magnetic Direction Finding and Time of Arrival techniques and is capable of producing the following parameters: latitude, longitude, microsecond time, peak current, polarity, number of sensors used, Cloud/Cloud-to-Ground indication, and multiplicity for lightning strikes.

Based on the last published performance characteristic evaluation results [2] it has a flash and stroke detection efficiencies of 92% and 76%, respectively, with a median absolute location error of 308 meters, the largest error was 4.2 kilometers, and the peak current estimation errors never exceeded 129%. It is worth noting the validation test was done at the ICLRT, at Camp Blanding, Florida, using rocket-triggered lightning data that are only representative of regular subsequent strokes in natural lightning. Consequently, the given performance characteristics a) are representative of the portion of the NLDN covering the Florida region shown in Fig. 3 (whose performance characteristics are not expected to be superior to those of the other parts of the network) and b) the flash detection efficiency is expected to be an underestimate of the true value for natural negative lightning flashes since first strokes typically have larger peak currents than subsequent ones.

III. DATA

During the year of 2011, from late March until December, the LPS was subjected to a total of 48 lightning flashes (8 direct and 40 nearby) with a total of 89 return strokes (19 direct and 70 nearby) recorded on 14 different days.

Each of the three towers of the LC39B LPS was struck directly by lightning at least once. About 17% of all the lightning flashes detected by the LC39B LPS attached directly to it (8 of 48 total flashes) all of which were negative flashes. About 63% of these direct strikes were multiple-stroke flashes (5 of 8) and only 20% of them (1 of 5) had all its return strokes (3) terminating in the same location.

CGLSS II and NLDN data were obtained for each day the LC39B LPS was directly struck by lightning. Data consist of a text file providing: date, time stamp (Coordinated Universal Time, UTC) with millisecond accuracy, decimal coordinates (latitude and longitude) with six significant figures, peak current (positive or negative) number of reporting sensors, cloud or ground discharge (only for NLDN), and error ellipse parameters.

The following CGLSS II and NLDN performance characteristics were analyzed: 1) flash and stroke detection efficiency, 2) location errors, and 3) differences in peak currents estimates. Both systems, CGLSS II and NLDN, were compared against LC39B LIS data. Each direct return stroke was correlated using Global Positioning System (GPS) time stamps to determine stroke detection efficiencies. Geographical coordinates were used to calculate location errors. Only 4 strokes (out of the 19 directly attached strokes) did not attach to the towers' air strike terminal. For those four events, downconductor current waveforms and video records were used to estimate their strike location.

LC39B LIS peak current values are calculated by algebraically adding the currents of all (9) downconductors. The sum of the downconductor currents for strokes with larger 10-90% rise times match better the incident current than for strokes with shorter rise times. The latter experience transmission line propagation effects, which may result in larger current magnitudes being measured at the ground level compared to the incident current.

Only one flash out of a total of 5 multiple-stroke direct flashes, ranging from a minimum of 2 to a maximum of 8 return strokes, had all return strokes (3) attaching to the same termination point with both CGLSS II and NLDN detecting 2 return strokes (the first and the third). For the remaining 4 multiple-stroke direct flashes the subsequent return strokes did not attach to the strike location of the first return stroke. Overall there were a total of 11 subsequent return strokes directly attaching to the LC39B LPS with 8 of them following the same channel as the previous return stroke.

There were two strokes attaching at two different locations simultaneously, both of these strokes were reported by the NLDN (one as cloud and one as ground discharge) but CGLSS II failed to report either of them. In both cases the attachment points were: 1) the air strike terminal atop the insulator of tower 2 (about 181 meters above ground level) and 2) ground level east and outside the LC39B perimeter about 560 and 615 meters (east and south-east, respectively) from tower 2. Tower 2 is the east-most tower of the LC39B LPS and its closest distance to the coast line is about 650 meters (north-east direction). For the purpose of this work, location calculations of these return strokes were made using the direct strike location on the LPS.

There was a two-stroke flash where the first stroke attached to the LC39B LPS and the subsequent stroke struck the ground, both CGLSS II and NLDN detected both strokes but only the first stroke is included in this publication. Additionally, there was a three-stroke flash where the first stroke attached to the LC39B LPS (tower 3), the second stroke had two simultaneous attachment points (tower 2 and nearby ground, 615 meters south-east of tower 2) and the third stroke struck the ground (at the same nearby location as the second stroke). CGLSS II reported only the first stroke and NLDN reported all three strokes. The third stroke of this flash is not included in this publication.

IV. RESULTS

The results presented in this paper are those corresponding only to direct strikes to the LC39B LPS. Pertaining to the NLDN data, the only data used for comparison purposes are those from reported ground strokes.

A. Flash and Stroke Detection Efficiencies

Table I shows the CGLSS II and NLDN flash detection efficiencies. Multiple return strokes are considered to be part of the same flash if the inter-stroke interval is less or equal than 500 milliseconds. Calculated inter-stroke interval from 11 subsequent strokes are: arithmetic mean 84, standard deviation 45, median 82, minimum 23 and maximum 180 milliseconds.

The criteria used to determine if either CGLSS II or NLDN detected a flash was if at least one of their detected strokes matched the UTC times of the LC39B LIS detected stroke.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF LC39B LPS DIRECT LIGHTNING STRIKES (MARCH-DECEMBER, 2011) WITH CGLSS II AND NLDN FLASH DETECTION EFFICIENCIES (DE).

Direct Lightning Flashes (March-December, 2011)	No. of Flashes	No. of NLDN Ground Flashes	NLDN Ground Flash DE	No. of CGLSS II Flashes	CGLSS II Flash DE
Total	8	6	75%	5	63%
Single-Stroke Flashes	3	1	33%	1	33%

The flash detection efficiency of the NLDN was 75% (6 of 8 total direct flashes), appreciably lower than 92% (34 of 37) reported from the most recent NLDN performance evaluation [2], the latter being considered an underestimate, since rocket triggered lightning data (2004-2009) were used. It is worth pointing out that if the ground/cloud categorization were ignored, then the NLDN flash detection efficiency would be 100% (8 of 8). The two missed ground strokes (both single-stroke flashes) were categorized as cloud events and one of

them had multiple simultaneous attachment points. Consequently, this ground/cloud categorization strongly affected the single-stroke flash detection efficiency going from 33% (1 of 3) to 100% (3 of 3) if the ground/cloud categorization is ignored. CGLSS II has the same 33% (1 of 3) detection efficiency for single-stroke flashes.

Table II shows the CGLSS II and NLDN stroke detection efficiencies for all strokes, first, subsequent and also those having multiple simultaneous attachment points.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF LC39B LPS DIRECT STRIKES (MARCH-DECEMBER, 2011) WITH CGLSS II AND NLDN STROKE DETECTION EFFICIENCIES (DE).

Direct Return Strikes (March-December, 2011)	No. of Strikes	No. of NLDN Ground Strikes	NLDN Ground Stroke DE	No. of CGLSS II Strikes	CGLSS II Stroke DE
Total	19	14	74%	12	63%
First	8	6	75%	5	63%
Subsequent	11	8	73%	7	64%
Multiple simultaneous attachment points	2	1	50%	0	0%

Figure 4. Histograms of the total number of strokes directly attaching to the LC30B LPS (a) detected by CGLSS II (b) and NLDN (c) versus rise-time (10%-90%). The rise-time was obtained from the LC39B LPS total calculated incident current.

For the NLDN, the total stroke detection efficiency is 74% (14 of 19 total direct strokes) which is very close to the results based on the most recent NLDN performance evaluation [2] and coincidentally very similar to the flash detection efficiency (see Table I). Additionally, the LC39B LIS allows us to segregate first and subsequent strokes, obtaining stroke detection efficiencies of 75% (6 of 8) and 73% (8 of 11), respectively. Again, it is worth noting that if the ground/cloud categorization were ignored, the calculated stroke detection efficiency would improve to 84% (16 of 19) and 100% (8 of 8) for all and first strokes, respectively.

For CGLSS II, the stroke detection efficiency is 63% (12 of 19 total direct strokes), coincidentally the same as the flash detection efficiency (see Table I), maintaining this number for the detection efficiency of first strokes and improving to 64% (7 of 11) for subsequent strokes.

The NLDN outperformed CGLSS II with 50% (1 of 2) detection efficiency for strokes with multiple simultaneous attachment points. Again, if the ground/cloud categorization were ignored, then NLDN's calculated detection efficiency would be 100% (2 of 2).

Fig. 4 shows the distribution of the LC39B LIS, CGLSS II, and NLDN detected strokes (a, b and c, respectively) versus the LC39B LPS total measured incident current rise-time. Rise-times were between 1.07 and 6.04 microseconds with arithmetic mean of 2.87, standard deviation of 1.9 and median of 2 microseconds.

B. Location Accuracy

Fig. 5 shows a spatial distribution of locations for all the direct strokes detected by CGLSS II (12) and all the ground strokes detected by the NLDN (14). The origin (X at the center of Fig. 5) corresponds to the known strike location at LC39B.

Figure 5. Stroke location errors of detected CGLSS II (12) and NLDN (14) direct strikes to LC39B LPS. The origin is indicated by a cross and indicates the actual strike location. The horizontal axis corresponds to the east-west component of the location error (positive values correspond to the east). The vertical axis corresponds to the north-south component of the location error (positive values correspond to the north). The arrow indicates the north. Statistics given are arithmetic mean (AM), standard deviation (SD), and median.

Strike locations of events captured while the dH/dt and dE/dt stations had not been activated where estimated using video records and if the events were within the field of view of cameras that had not been deployed, downconductors current waveforms were used to estimate the strike location. The locations were estimated to be about half the distance from the tower to the downconductor grounding point for the two strikes to the downconductors. Lack of video records for one of these events was a result of upset electronics of the communication system that controls the camera caused by a previous direct strike to one of the towers. After this event, efforts were made to improve the immunity of the communication system, which is a service provided to the LC39B LIS by the KSC communication infrastructure. After modifications were made to the communication infrastructure to improve their immunity to direct strikes to the LC39B LPS, no other loss of communication has been observed.

Fig. 6 shows the histogram of GCLSS II and NLDN absolute stroke location errors for the 12 and 14 strokes shown in Fig. 5. CGLSS II outperforms NLDN regarding location errors with minimum, median and maximum location errors of 51, 155 and 467 meters (for CGLSS II) compared to 133, 405 and 1,714 meters (for the NLDN), the latter to be compared to 23, 308 and 4,239 meters presented in [2].

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 are the analogous of Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 but only for subsequent strokes following the same channel as a previous stroke. Ideally the CGLSS II and the NLDN should locate all these strokes in the same position since all these strokes follow the channel of the previous stroke. The CGLSS II and NLDN minimum, median and maximum location errors were 159, 256 and 467 meters and 133, 487 and 980 meters, respectively. These errors can be interpreted as erroneous multiple earth striking locations for flashes whose subsequent strokes followed the same path as the first stroke.

March-December, 2011		NLDN	CGLSS
N-S	AM, m	-145	-20
	SD, m	325	90
	Median, m	-143	-36
E-W	AM, m	124	73
	SD, m	619	213
	Median, m	58	85
N		14	12

March-December, 2011	NLDN	CGLSS
AM, m	572	190
SD, m	420	143
Median, m	405	155
Min, m	133	51
Max, m	1714	467
N	14	12

Figure 6. Histograms of absolute location errors for direct return strokes to LC39B LPS detected by CGLSS II (12) and NLDN (14). Statistics given are arithmetic mean (AM), standard deviation (SD) median, minimum, and maximum.

Fig. 9 shows the absolute location error with respect to the number of reporting sensors. The range of reporting sensors was 2-5 for the CGLSS II and 2-15 for the NLDN, with the largest absolute location error corresponding to an event in which 15 sensors contributed to the solution for the NLDN. These results do not show the expected correlation in which the location error is expected to decrease as the number of reporting sensors increases, for both CGLSS II and NLDN.

Fig. 10 shows the absolute location error with respect to the rise-time of the LC39B LIS calculated total current to ground where CGLSS II location errors tend to decrease as the rise time increases. On the other hand, NLDN's location errors seem to increase at both extremes, the slowest and fastest strokes.

March-December, 2011		NLDN	CGLSS
N-S	AM, m	-35	-50
	SD, m	384	109
	Median, m	-89	-100
E-W	AM, m	211	125
	SD, m	488	293
	Median, m	136	127
N		6	6

Figure 7. Stroke location errors of subsequent strokes following the same channel as its previous stroke and detected by CGLSS II (6) and NLDN (6). All these strokes attached directly to the LC39B LPS. The origin is indicated by a cross and indicates the actual strike location. The horizontal axis corresponds to the east-west component of the location error (positive values correspond to the east). The vertical axis corresponds to the north-south component of the location error (positive values correspond to the north). The arrow indicates the north. Statistics given are arithmetic mean (AM), standard deviation (SD), and median.

March-December, 2011	NLDN	CGLSS
AM, m	510	287
SD, m	358	143
Median, m	487	256
Min, m	133	159
Max, m	980	467
N	6	6

Figure 8. Histograms of absolute location errors for direct subsequent strokes to LC39B LPS following the same channel as its previous stroke and detected by CGLSS II (6) and NLDN (6). Statistics given are arithmetic mean (AM), standard deviation (SD) median, minimum, and maximum.

Figure 9. Absolute location error versus the number of reporting sensors for CGLSS II and NLDN.

Figure 10. Absolute location error versus the calculated rise-time (10%-90%) of the LC39B LPS calculated total current to ground.

C. Peak Current Estimates

Fig. 11 shows the peak current difference for each of the two systems, CGLSS II and NLDN, and the LC39B LIS. Both, CGLSS II and NLDN, underestimate the peak current by 10%-40%. It is important to point out that the LC39B LIS calculated current to ground is the arithmetic sum of all the currents to ground measured at the nine downconductors. There is one event for which the NLDN measured a higher current than the LC39B LIS and this corresponds to a stroke with two simultaneous attachment points; there was another similar event but the NLDN categorized it as a cloud flash, hence it is not included in this plot. CGLSS II did not detect any of the strokes with multiple simultaneous attachment points.

Figure 11. Peak current difference in percent for both CGLSS II and NLDN reported peak currents using the LC39B LPS peak current (calculated total incident current) as reference. For one event NLDN shows a positive difference, this is due to that event having simultaneous multiple attaching points (tower 2 and nearby ground). Only 11 and 13 return strokes instead of 12 and 14 (CGLSS II and NLDN respectively) are included here due to LC39B LPS current saturation for one event.

Fig. 12 shows a histogram for all the LC39B LIS recorded strokes and their corresponding range of peak currents and it identifies the range of peak currents for which CGLSS II and NLDN detected strokes. The largest recorded current saturated the LC39B LIS at 174.3 kA and, excluding this and the events with simultaneous ground attachment points, the median LC39B LIS calculated peak current was about 29.1 kA.

Fig. 13 shows a relation between LC39B LIS calculated peak currents and the number of reporting sensors for each system, CGLSS II and NLDN.

Figure 12. Detected strokes as a function of LC39B LIS measured peak current. For each peak current range (bin size of 15 kA) the ratio inside the bars indicates the number of strokes detected by CGLSS II (numerator) and NLDN (denominator) for that peak current range.

Figure 13. LC39B LIS measured peak current (calculated total current to ground) versus the number of sensors detecting that event for CGLSS II and NLDN.

To further evaluate the performance of CGLSS II and NLDN, the 19 return strokes, which attached directly to the LC39B LIS, were reorganized with the following definitions: first strokes are those that create a new channel or strokes that

do not follow the same path of a previous stroke; subsequent strokes are those that follow the same path, or channel, as a preceding return stroke. This reorganization results in 11 first and 8 subsequent return strokes of which: CGLSS II did not detect 5 first and 2 subsequent return strokes and the NLDN did not detect 3 first and 2 subsequent return strokes. Considering only the 18 LC39B LIS recorded strokes, in which there was no saturation, the number of strokes detected by CGLSS and NLDN eligible for comparisons were 11 and 12, respectively.

With this new first and subsequent return strokes categorization and using the LC39B LIS sum of all the currents to ground as the total incident current, both CGLSS II and NLDN peak currents are compared to the LC39B LIS measurements. The comparisons between the LC39B LIS “peak incident current” and the estimated CGLSS II and NLDN peak currents are presented in Fig. 14. Also, the apparent underestimation in Fig. 14 are plotted vs. the 10%-90% rise-times in Fig. 15. The NLDN seems to show a reasonable peak current underestimation (less than 20%) for all the subsequent return strokes following the same path, or channel, as the preceding return stroke, which have considerable faster 10-90% rise-times than first strokes. This can be explained by the fact that triggered lightning has been a calibration method used over the years by this system and the nature of classic rocket-triggered lightning is comparable to subsequent return strokes. Nevertheless, the errors when estimating the peak current of first strokes, or slower 10-90% rise-times are considerably larger. This is an area that will be studied in more detail in the future.

Figure 14. CGLSS II and NLDN peak current percent underestimation for selected direct return strokes to LC39B during 2011 based on LC39B LIS calculated peak current organized by a) first and b) subsequent return strokes.

Figure 15. CGLSS II and NLDN peak current percent underestimation for selected direct return strokes to LC39B during 2011 based on LC39B LPS calculated 10%-90% current rise-time organized by a) first and b) subsequent return strokes.

Two of the five first return strokes not detected by CGLSS II were misclassified by the NLDN as cloud discharges. It is worth noting that one of these return strokes had a simultaneous nearby attachment to ground. Neither CGLSS II nor the NLDN detected a first stroke (new channel) with a measured peak current and 10%-90% rise-time of 19.3 kA and 1.5 microseconds, respectively. This particular stroke did not follow the same path as a previous stroke. Another of the first return strokes not detected by CGLSS II was a 28.8 kA stroke with a 10-90% rise-time of 2 microseconds, with no LC39B LIS evidence of a preceding return stroke. The other first return stroke not detected by CGLSS II had a simultaneous nearby attachment point to ground and the NLDN detected this event and reported a peak current of almost twice what was reported by LC39B LIS.

Neither CGLSS II nor the NLDN detected two subsequent strokes (following the same path as a previous stroke) with peak currents and 10%-90% rise-times of 13.5 kA, 13.4 kA and 1.08 μ s and 1.43 μ s, respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The lightning instrumentation recently installed at LC39B, Kennedy Space Center, FL, provides ground-truth data, which were used to evaluate the detection efficiency and location errors of the CGLSS II and the NLDN from March to

December of 2011. Realizing the small sample size, the LC39B LIS acquired data seem to indicate that the stroke detection efficiency of either the CGLSS II or the NLDN (63% and 74%, respectively, with both systems experiencing a 33% detection efficiency of single-stroke flashes) is lower than expected, especially since these two systems are used to monitor lightning activity and to locate cloud-to-ground strokes near launch pads at KSC and CCAFS. Also, it seems like both systems, CGLSS II and NLDN tend to underestimate the channel base peak current by about -40 to -10%. Out of the 19 strokes recorded, 8 were first strokes and 11 were subsequent strokes. Peak current estimation for CGLSS II and NLDN seem to be better for subsequent strokes than for first strokes. One direct stroke saturated two of the nine LC39B downconductor transient current measurements. The peak of the sum of the currents to ground for this particular event was 174.3 kA, but a reasonable extrapolation of the two saturated downconductor current measurements makes this a 200-220 kA negative stroke. The median of all 18 direct strokes (excluding the event that saturated the downconductor currents) is about 30 kA, with rise-times between 1 and 6 microseconds, with an arithmetic mean of about 2.9 microseconds (the rise-time is measured as the 10%-90% of the sum of currents to ground). Inter-stroke time intervals were between 23 and 180 milliseconds, with an arithmetic mean of 84 milliseconds. The CGLSS II and NLDN minimum, median, and maximum absolute location errors for all detected return strokes were 51, 155, 467 and 133, 405, 1,714 meters, respectively. Also, the CGLSS II and NLDN minimum, median, and maximum absolute location errors for subsequent strokes following the same channel as the previous stroke were 159, 256, 467 and 133, 487, 980 meters, respectively. During 2011 (from late March until December) the LC39B LPS was struck by 19 strokes, but the lightning instrumentation system detected additional 70 strokes, which did not attach to the LC39B LPS directly. The 70 nearby strokes are being analyzed to increase the sample size and obtain a better estimate of detection efficiency for both, CGLSS II and NLDN. Future publications will include the analysis of some of these nearby strokes as well as future direct strikes to the LC39B LPS. Although the fidelity of the stroke detection efficiency calculations is very high, the flash detection efficiency calculation is still being investigated due to the complexity of the assessment.

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